

Archiving, sharing and discussing research data on Eastern Europe, South Caucasus and Central Asia

Data Review

Data Citation

Nathalie Rathkamp (2025): Review of Lviv Center for Urban History (2014): Intimate Chronologies of the Euromaidan (published on Discuss Data), v. 1.0, Discuss Data, <https://doi.org/10.48320/C2F59F7D-9C31-472B-BFAB-82FD7C72795C>

Abstract

The “Intimate Chronologies of the Euromaidan” is an interview collection covering the protests in Ukraine against the decision to suspend the signing of the Association Agreement with the EU, also known as the Euromaidan protests. The dataset - created by a research team around the project leaders Natalia Otrishchenko, Ana Susak and Hana Josticova – and put together by the Center for Urban History in Lviv, aims to depict the diverse personal stories, emotions, and expectations of the various protest participants (Otrishchenko 2024). The data is available in the form of a gallery that lists all relevant quotes from the conducted interviews sorted by different categories (3). In total the dataset contains 145 in-depth interviews (Otrishchenko 2024). As of summer 2024, work on the data collection seems to have concluded. The data review includes a link to the “Intimate Chronologies of the Euromaidan” website from which the dataset, as well as additional information, is available for download. A free registration is however required to download the raw data.

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Data Review – Intimate Chronologies of the Euromaidan

The “Intimate Chronologies of the Euromaidan” is an Interview Collection covering the protests in Ukraine against the decision to suspend the signing of the Association Agreement with the EU, also known as the Euromaidan protests. The dataset - created by a research team around the project leaders Natalia Otrishchenko and Ana Susak – and put together by the Center for Urban History of East Central Europe, aims to depict the diverse personal stories, emotions, and expectations of the various protest participants (Otrishchenko 2024). In total the dataset contains 145 in-depth interviews (Otrishchenko 2024).

The first wave of interviews was conducted in December 2013 and also includes five interviews with Euromaidan activists in Warsaw and Lublin (Poland), since the protest gathered considerable resonance abroad. The questions asked during the interview focused on “practices and forms of participation in EuroMaidan and similar events, motivations and emotional experiences, the importance of certain places, evaluation of slogans, opinions about European integration and European values, and hopes for the future” (2).

The second wave of interviews was conducted in February 2014 (Otrishchenko 2024) and included a questionnaire - as well as a projective drawing while conducting the study in Kyiv – which allowed for analysis of “the symbolic and cognitive dimensions of the perception of spaces where the events unfolded”. Furthermore, questions about “possible changes in relation to the state and society under the influence of events on Maidan, about groups of protesters, heroes and antiheroes of Maidan and Ukraine and historical parallels” (2) were added (2).

For the interviews the method of in-depth interviews during the protest was chosen, to depict the ‘here and now’ with the participants and activists of the Euromaidan. The interviewees were selected from the participants according to the quota principle (quotas for age and gender), and activists and organizers were approached via personal contacts. The sampling is meant to show the range of opinions and motivations of participants in a particular city at a specific time through individual accounts rather than collective actions (Otrishchenko 2024).

The material was gathered in written form, anonymised and organised into 17 thematic categories (Otrishchenko 2024), with the three overarching categories of whether a quote was (a) ideational, (b) operational or (c) city-specific (2). Some of the questions were however very specific to particular events. If that was the case, the answers to these questions were assigned their own category (e.g. Leninopad, Hrushevskoho). This allocation of the data shows the rationale behind the database: The data being sorted by meaning instead of by question (3).

In order to achieve this the gathered data has been assigned to different categories. These categories include:

- Attitudes toward “Leninopad”

- Maidan heroes and antiheroes
- Heroes and antiheroes in the history of Ukraine
- Memorable events during the protest
- Motivation of mobilization
- Forms of participation in the protest
- Perception of Ukraine and other states
- Organization of mobilization
- Perception of European integration and European values
- Events at Hrushevsky Street and violence
- Protest spaces
- Ideas about the Euromaidan Opponents
- Characteristics of cities and differences between cities
- Maidan symbols and slogans
- Identities of protest participants
- Sources of (un)reliable information about events
- Expectations for the future and desired changes

Each category contains a short description upfront, which contains information such as in which wave of the interviews the answers within this category were gathered, as well as which questions get answered and to what purpose this information was collected. Underneath that you will find a gallery of all the relevant quotes for this category. Each quote comes with relevant information about the interviewees gender, age and role during the protest, as well as the date on which the data was gathered (3). The interview answers within the different categories are divided from one another by three dots: '...', and any further information added – to clarify the topic that a given answer addresses - is marked by square brackets: '[]'.

While the data may not be representative, the research team tried to convey the specific situation of each city protest and to represent various groups of protesters (2). The database introduces new knowledge, thus enabling new qualitative research approaches. With its approach of focusing on personal narratives, it helps researchers understand the origins of social movements as well as the changes in the meaning of the Euromaidan and the motivations and objectives of its participants over time (3).

Sources:

- (1) Otrishchenko, Natalia. 2024. DataLabBLOG: Sources from Inside the Protest: The Euromaidan Interview Collection. <https://konkoop.de/index.php/blog/sources-from-inside-the-protest-the-euromaidan-interview-collection/>. Last accessed 13.09.2024.

- (2) Center for Urban History of East Central Europe. Intimate Chronologies of the Euromaidan website: <https://www.lvivcenter.org/en/academic-en/research/voices-of-resistance-and-hope/>. Last accessed 13.09.2024.
- (3) Center for Urban History. Intimate Chronologies of the Euromaidan. <https://uma.lvivcenter.org/en/collections/146/interviews>. Last accessed 30.11.2024